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Building the
digital future of
catalysis

<https://nfdi4cat.org/>

Dear reader,

This is the very first issue of the NFDI4Cat newsletter! In this inaugural issue, we cordially invite you to our first **NFDI4Cat Annual Meeting** on November 17th. The test run of the **Catalysis Research Data Management School** took place on the 22nd of September at the Southwest German Catalysis Institute in Annweiler am Trifels. And last but not least, the first **four sections within the NFDI association have been successfully established** and have already started their work.

You can read about these news and get more updates in our newsletter below! We hope you enjoy reading it,

Your NFDI4Cat management team

NFDI4Cat Annual Meeting

It has been one year since NFDI4Cat started! We would like to share with you, the public, the scientific community, and all relevant initiatives what we have achieved so far. Therefore, we would like to cordially invite you to our first NFDI4Cat annual meeting which will take place on on November 17th. In addition to the NFDI4Cat representatives sharing their results, Dr. Sandip De from BASF will be giving a keynote presentation on the Digital Transformation of Catalysis and Materials Sciences. Don't forget to register!

[I want to participate](#)

NFDI e.V. sections now launched

At the beginning of October, the first four sections within the NFDI association were established. These four sections are:

- (Meta)daten, Terminologien und Provenienz (section-metadata)
- Common Infrastructures (section-infra)
- Training & Education (section-edutrain)
- Ethical, Legal & Social Aspects (section-ELSA)

These four common cross-cutting themes will be worked on across the boundaries of each consortium. Representatives of different consortia are active in each section. Close cooperation is intended to exploit synergy effects and identify follow-up potential. All four section-concepts have been published in Zenodo.

[Let's read them](#)

Research School of Catalysis - A Runtest

On September 22, 2021, the RDM School of Catalysis started a first test run as part of the South-West German Catalysis Institute in Annweiler at Trifels. Within 160 minutes, including open discussion and interactive examples, the 15 participants from different institutions received insights into research data management in the field of catalysis.

[I would like to know more](#)

Events

GeCatS-Infotag "CO₂-Neutral Chemical Industry" on November 16, 2021 - [register now!](#)

55th Annual Meeting of German Catalysts

2022 on March 16 - 18, 2022 - **submit papers now!**

NaWuReT YounGeCatS Summerschool
2022 on May 23 - 25, 2022 - **save the date!**

27th North American Catalysis Society
Meeting on May 22-27, 2022 - **submit your abstract now!**

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